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CORROSION OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL BRONZES FROM SAROUQ AL-HADID AND AL-QUSAIS (DUBAI, UAE)

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides a comparative overview of the state of conservation of metal artifacts from two sites with long occupations in Dubai, namely Sarouq Al-Hadid and Al-Qusais. In particular, the aim is to comprehensively understand the corrosion behaviour of bronze objects in connection with their burial environment. Both sites present different soil types and rates of corrosivity, which was determined to have a significant impact, as demonstrated by the compositional analyses of both the archaeological context and the artifacts. Archaeometric methods used to reach conclusions on surface morphologies and corrosion layer formation were optical microscopy combined with X-ray diffraction and fluorescence, in addition to ICP spectroscopy. Results indicate a connection between soil composition and corrosion dynamic, pointing to the need for tailored approaches to restoration and conservation.

KEYWORDS: Soil Corrosivity, Metals, Conservation, XRD, XRF, SEM-EDS, ICP.

1. INTRODUCTION

The main purpose of this paper is to compare the surrounding soil media of two archaeological sites in Dubai and their influence on the corrosion of buried bronze objects, as part of a larger study in archaeological metals conservation in the emirate of Dubai (Salmin, 2024). Resulting observations may help prepare a solution of a corrosion inhibitor other than benzotriazole (BTA). This process refers to an irreversible corrosion process occurring by contact with chlorides, understood scientifically for decades (MacLeod, 1981) but still today lacking any definitive treatment, namely for archaeological objects (Jiachang *et al.*, 2024). The current research process involved studying the morphology and metal content of selected artifacts and testing the soil corrosivity associated with these artifacts. Specifically, the study determined the corrosion products on the bronze artifacts and assessed the soil conditions at the excavations of both sites (pH, salinity, texture, composition, and moisture content). Results yield insights into the nature of the corrosion of bronze artifacts in the region of Dubai and allow for considering specific inhibitors in the conservation process. The materials under scrutiny in this paper originate from two geographically different sites. While Saruq Al-Hadid (SHS) is located in a remote sand dune environment, Al-Qusais (QUS) lies in a sabkha area, that is, in a wide coastal flatland that has been recently urbanized. These environmental differences are analysed as a factor for metal corrosion development and lead to more informed conservation options. Artifact composition and surface damage require either the use of chemicals or alternative treatments for the mitigation of corrosion, but this needs to be assessed based on the knowledge of combined external agents. While the strict archaeological importance of both sites has been highlighted, the long-term conservational aspects of metals from these south-eastern Arabian sites have yielded increased attention in recent years (Lois *et al.*, 2020; Sayama *et al.*, 2022). Comparable exercises on archaeological copper alloys carried out in other geographical environments (e.g., Salem and Abd Allah, 2021; Rifai *et al.*, 2022; Çakaj *et al.*, 2023; suggest that the environment is indeed a key factor in corrosion dynamics. Corrosion analysis and “bronze disease” in particular are a well-studied topic in archaeological conservation, with increasing experimentation on both diagnostics and treatments (Liu *et al.*, 2021; Monari *et al.*, 2023), however mitigation of corrosion through environmental control depends on post-excavation contexts. Computational simulations (Wang *et al.*, 2023)

clearly demonstrate a wide range of corrosion reactions yet they all are mainly determined by chemical / environmental characteristics.

2. THEORETICAL OVERVIEW

The identified archaeological sites in the emirate of Dubai have been excavated, either in open area strategies or through test trenches (Juchniewicz and Lic, 2023; Valente *et al.*, 2023; Weeks *et al.* 2024), which has produced challenges to the conservation of structures and objects. This paper deals with bronzes, produced regionally and with varying compositions, especially regarding the proportion of tin alloyed with copper (Turner-Walker, 2008). In general terms, their corrosion results from a natural oxidation reaction or an electrochemical reaction between the metal and any surrounding oxidizing media, either air, water, or soil. Less noble metals corrode more rapidly, also depending on the oxidizing agent and the electrolyte (Nord *et al.*, 2005). In archaeological copper alloy objects, corrosion represents a complex mechanism that forms layers of different products with several shapes and weakening morphologies. In severe cases, corrosion can lead to the oxidation of an entire object with no metallic remnant (Oudbashi, 2015; Selwyn, 2004). Artifacts from both Sarouq Al-Hadid and Al-Qusais interacted for millennia with their immediate environment, undergoing slow degradation reactions underground. As the metals in the objects corrode, the released positive ions from the corroded surface migrate to the surrounding soil, raising the pH value and transforming the metal ions into insoluble and solid corrosion products, forming a hard crust around the object surface. Several factors affect the corrosion rate in the burial environment: the chemical reachability of the metal or alloy (its standard electrode potential), the availability of oxygen, the conductivity of the surrounding soil (water content and dissolved ions), the permeability to water and oxygen of the corrosion layers formed between the metal and the environment, pH, temperature, and the contact with dissimilar metals (Turner-Walker, 2008).

In the case of the objects used in this paper, the corrosion of typical copper alloys such as bronze leads to the so-called “bronze disease”. The combination of water, oxygen, and carbon dioxide in the archaeological layers, in addition to dissolved salts, especially chloride ions, accelerate the corrosion reactions and influence the nature of the corrosion products. Archaeological case studies (Doménech-Carbó *et al.*, 2008; Sandu *et al.*, 2008; Carvalho, 2023) have repeatedly demonstrated the response of products of such bronze corrosion, which typically includes azurite, malachite, atacamite and clinoatacamite. Normally,

copper oxides are formed in two oxidation states: copper (I), formed as Cu_2O , and copper (II), with a high concentration of Cu^{2+} . In copper (I), the chloride ion acts as a catalyst for Cu_2O , which will produce nanokite (CuCl) as a corrosion product, which is usually stable in arid environments. In the presence of moisture, CuCl will transform to Cu_2O (3), liberating hydrochloric acid (HCl), thus lowering the pH value. HCl will react with further Cu to produce more nanokite (CuCl) (4). All these reactions will produce corrosion products as per the following equations (1)-(4):

The liberated HCl will produce more nanokite (CuCl) directly.

Several types of bronze corrosion product formation are known, such as cuprite (malachite, azurite), copper trihydroxychlorides (atacamite), and nanokite, depending on the different factors associated with the surrounding soil (Oudbashi, 2015). It is therefore important to consider the soil corrosivity in direct connection with environmental threats to archaeological remains (Watkinson & Corfield, 2008). Soil-induced corrosion depends on the metallurgical characteristics of the artifact and involves chemical reactions with the surrounding elements (Corrosionpedia, 2014), leading to classifications of the soil as non-corrosive, partially or severely corrosive. Determining parameters include soil texture, pH, soluble salts, soil moisture, electrical conductivity, burial duration, the artifact's chemical composition, and the presence of microorganisms (Papadopoulou et al., 2016). As different corrosion mechanisms occur, the greatest concern is when copper reacts with chloride, forming basic copper chlorides and copper oxides as active corrosion products (Oudbashi, 2018). Another typical example of a corrosion product of copper is brochantite (copper hydroxide sulphate), formed by the reaction of copper with acidic sulphur compounds, while copper chloride layers are formed at high humidity in the presence of chlorine. As is the case in the funerary contexts studied below, bone degradation will increase the phosphate deposition leading to reactions with copper resulting in copper phosphates in the form of corrosion layers (Fan & Freestone, 2017; Nord et al., 2005).

The current paper integrates these factors by calculating a Soil Corrosivity Index (SCI; Oudbashi, 2018) for soils at both studied excavation sites. The first parameters influencing soil corrosivity are the soil texture and its aeration. Aeration is related to the presence of oxygen and water drainages from the soil to

the bedrock (Turner-Walker, 2008). This unavoidably increases the corrosion rate and, inversely, its reduction will decrease the corrosivity rate (Gerwin & Baumhauer, 2000). Three main types of soil, that is, sand, silt, and clay equally produce variation in the corrosion rate. The size of soil grains plays a role in allowing water and oxygen access to the buried artifacts, thus potentially enhancing corrosion. It must be noted that in sandy soil and aerated environments, the artifacts are more corroded than in a poorly aerated environment (Nord et al., 2005). The second type of influences relates to water content and humidity, which are indirectly related to aeration, and labels the water-holding capacity of the soil. Silt presents a high water-holding capacity, so the soil is highly corrosive. On the other hand, clay has low aeration, because it has a high drainage rate and a low ability to hold water. Thus, few corrosive mechanisms occur in a clay environment. Also, the depth of the buried artifact is related to the humidity of the surroundings, which in turn creates a more corrosive environment. The third major type of influence is soil acidity, responsible for up to 90% of bronze corrosion. As a general rule, the more acidic the soil, the more corrosive, and when the pH is neutral the corrosion rate will tendentially decrease. A fourth sort of impact results from electrical conductivity, based on the soluble salt content and thus on soil salinity, which means that acids and salts enhance corrosion.

In addition to these conditions, multiple other influences, such as environmental threats, can significantly affect soil corrosivity in areas with anthropogenic activity. Some corrosive agents or factors, namely phosphorus and salts are easily transported through the atmosphere and end up penetrating the soil. Salt and soot (carbon) increase acidification and electric conductivity. Also, chloride and sulphate concentrations, which promote corrosion, are comparatively high in urban areas. Excavated artifacts near roads typically contain higher chloride content, and pollution can greatly affect the corrosion of archaeological objects. This combined reality explains why fairly close-by locations can exhibit different corrosion mechanisms (Gerwin & Baumhauer, 2000).

3. ARCHAEOLOGICAL CONTEXT

Two sites in the emirate of Dubai were selected to study the soil corrosivity and the corrosion effect on archaeological bronze objects. While Saruq Al-Hadid was excavated in a full desert setting, Al-Qusais is situated in an area adjacent to the Gulf coast and enveloped by urban infrastructures (Fig. 1). Both sites had multiple occupations but the materials studied in this paper connect to the Iron Age II phases. Geographically, Saruq Al-Hadid is located in an area of live sand dunes that rise to about forty meters in height

and cover historical features and artifacts at the site. This site presents very little vegetation besides small shrubs and some Ghaf trees (*Prosopis cineraria*), which have deep roots that penetrate the dunes to reach the water. In addition, there are wild shrubs that grow after rainfall. The main occupation brackets were defined as 1100-600 BC (Weeks *et al.*, 2017). The site is 60 km from Dubai city and 45 km from the nearest coastline. Ancient artifacts are spread discontinuously over a large area of approximately 6.2 sq. km. The central area at Saruq Al-Hadid was covered with a huge quantity of black slag, which represents the waste residue of copper smelting activities. Other materials found at the site include metallurgical debris of

raw copper lumps and ingots, fragments of iron artifacts, and other anthropic remains, mostly pottery sherds, limestone blocks, and mortars.

The site's maximum altitude is 108.5 meters above sea level. It includes a gradual slope towards the western sector, where a flat level is covered thick coat of gypsum, connected to a thin layer of compacted sand and pebbles (Herrmann *et al.*, 2012). At the time of discovery, large quantities of archaeological remains were spread over this sandy deposit. The site currently displays an administrative building, a temporary storage, a small conservation laboratory, a small museum, and accommodation quarters.

Figure 1. Location of Saruq Al-Hadid (red) and Al-Qusais (yellow)

Survey and excavation projects at this important Dubai site recovered more than 20,000 objects, about 70% of which are made of metal (bronze, copper alloy, iron, gold, and silver). Among the significant objects are large collections of iron artifacts, including swords, daggers, spearheads, and arrowheads, confirming that SHS was an area of manufacture and a trading centre during the Iron Age. Many differently sized bronze and golden snake-shaped objects reflect a religious ritual related to the snake cult practiced during the Iron Age, a reality that has been documented all across the region (Benoist, 2007; Cian,

2015). Archaeometallurgical studies of slags, furnaces, crucibles, and dross found at the site have revealed the composition of the metal objects, not only of gold and iron but also the ubiquitous copper alloys. The analyses provide an insight into the manufacturing techniques and the source of the raw materials. Preliminary studies of bronze items indicate that most archaeological pieces were made of pure copper or copper alloyed with tin and possibly zinc. Also, several slag pieces collected from different layers have been analysed (Franke *et al.*, 2016).

Conversely, the Al-Qusais funerary site is located 13 km northeast of Deira in a coastal sabkha or salt marsh area. It is part of a modern cemetery, which occupies a large part of the site. Settlement dates back to the Late Bronze Age and the early Iron Age (1600 - 550 BC). It is considered one of the most important archaeological sites in Dubai, and one of the first excavated in the Emirate. The site comprises a small temple dedicated to the Iron Age cult of the snake. The initial artifacts were discovered during the excavation for modern burials, including stone vessels with engraved designs, some copper alloy arrowheads, pottery, and copper alloy objects. Excavation started in 1973 by an Iraqi mission (Potts, 2012). From 1990 to 1994, a Dubai Museum team resumed excavation inside the modern cemetery boundaries along its southern wall to define and separate the archaeological area from the modern cemetery and prevent future expansion into the archaeological site. Excavations resulted in the identification of two additional funerary locations totalling 120 individual burials dating from the second half of the 2nd millennium to the early 1st millennium BC. Many differences are visible between these burials and those found previously in terms of their shape, size, burial methods and construction, body orientation, burial style, and quality and quantity of grave finds. They were identified at depths of 40-150 cm. It is suggested that individuals and communities in that area who buried their dead lived under different and changing beliefs during the Late Bronze Age and early Iron Age. Most newly found objects correspond to funerary gifts and include pottery such as vessels, bowls, jugs, cups, and incense burners. Also, a collection of soft stone objects mainly made of chlorite schist, such as different kinds of vessels, cups, and bowls, was found. Some of them are decorated on their surfaces with different patterns. The excavation also revealed different kinds of jewellery, such as gemstone beads and pendants, bronze bracelets, and rings, along with marine shells. Some of them were filled with green or black material, and others had engraved decorations. These artifacts were often found close to the head or chest of the deceased. Of interest to this paper are the metal objects, mainly copper alloy tools and weapons such as daggers, spearheads, and arrowheads. Some of the copper alloy arrowheads still have remains of wooden pieces on their tangs and were discovered in assemblages. They most likely had been placed in a leather quiver that rotted away. Daggers were found obliquely in all the burials. A round-shaped seashell, convex and well-polished on one face and decorated with circles and dots inlaid with lobes of gemstone had been placed near each dagger. Also, daily life objects made of bronze or copper alloy were found at the site, such as cups, spouted bowls, vessels, knives, and needles.

Regarding provenance, the Iron Age copper metallurgy across Southeast Arabia is based mainly on local and regional ores, as has been repeatedly demonstrated at large producing sites in the nowadays UAE and Oman (Lehner et al., 2023).

4. SAMPLES AND METHODS

4.1. Sampling

For this analytical study, several soil samples were collected from separate areas at each site, given the following desert specificities and avoiding surface contexts. The soil of Saruq Al-Hadid is that of a dynamic landscape with live sand dunes, which includes several stratigraphic layers. The collected samples were all taken from areas within one stratigraphic layer and due to the nature of the site posing few limitations as far as quantity is concerned; more than 1kg per area was collected. This was carried out in Saruq-7 G and F, at both excavated and unexcavated squares (Fig. 2). All samples were taken at depths of 10 cm. The stratigraphy was defined as linear, with a first layer directly under the dune, and a second layer, which runs deeper. The samples were collected in plastic bags and separated through a 2 mm mesh sieve. Small stones were separated from the samples.

On the other hand, the Al-Qusais funerary area contains multiple tombs including two types of soil: the sabkha soil around the tomb and an area filled with loam sand to close the tomb. Samples taken of the latter soil type were more reduced in quantity because of technical feasibility and ethical reasonability within defined excavated structures (Fig. 3). Ten soil samples were collected from different areas and labelled according to the collection site. The samples were taken from the sabkha soil, considered as the tomb's wall, and a sandy layer inside two of the graves. The samples were collected in a plastic tube to prevent damaging the tomb and the skeletons within the tomb. Four samples were taken from Grave 309, Area F4. This individual grave has an oval shape and is partly uncovered and contains a skeleton in a flexed position and several artifacts. Three of the samples were retrieved inside the grave near the skeleton and a bronze artefact, while the last sample was from the wall of the grave. Secondly, a random soil sample was selected at the site from Area E. Thirdly, three soil samples were collected from grave No. G35 in area E7. This grave was excavated in 1991, and the skeleton found therein had been removed. It was therefore empty when the soil sample was collected, but a small metal fragment was found inside this grave. Local UAE geological properties are quite well-known, especially the opposition between sabkha and desert soils (Alsharhan et al., 2020; Alshenawy et al., 2021;)

Different bronze samples were collected from each site to understand the corrosion morphology of the bronze artifacts. Ten samples from each site were collected randomly from fragments of artifacts uncovered during the excavations at both sites (Figures 4 and 5). Following excavation, they were conserved in the study store of the Antiquities Department at the Dubai Culture and Art Authority (DCAA). Almost all

samples were covered with sand accumulation on a corroded layer. However, as discussed in the results section, not all samples exhibit the same corrosion morphology. For product identification, corrosion powder was collected from 8 samples, four from each site, to analyse them by X-ray diffraction (XRD). The powder products include the copper minerals of the corrosion and the attached soil product.

Figure 2. Sample collection area, Saruq Al-Hadid

Figure 3. Sample collection area, Al-Qusais

Figure 4. Sampled artifacts from Saruq Al-Hadid (Iron Age II)

Figure 5. Sampled artifacts from Al-Qusais (Iron Age II)

4.2. Measurements

Samples were weighed on Mettler PE 160 and Kern ABT 220-5DM balances. IR spectra of the soil samples were taken on a Nexus 670 FT-IR spectrometer from Thermo Nicolet and with a Spectrum Two instrument from Perkin Elmer. The samples were measured as KBr pellets. A Carbolite oven (ELF 11-6) was used for

drying and heating processes (eg., at 70 °C, 120 °C, and 600 °C). Drying of the samples at 37 °C was carried out in an EcoCell drying cabinet (Medcenter Einrichtungen GmbH, MMM group). pH values were obtained with a pH meter (Orion model 420A), and conductivities were measured with a conductivity meter (Orion model 50). Powder X-ray diffraction analysis

was carried out on a Rigaku Miniflex XRD, Japan, where the diffraction patterns of the samples were recorded with a Bragg's angle 2θ from 5° to 90° using Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$) at voltage 45 kV and 40 mA current. All the analyses were performed at ambient temperature. Scanning electron microscopy coupled with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDS) - SEM images were captured with a Thermo Quattro S instrument at high vacuum mode ($6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ Pa}$), with an accelerating voltage of 30kV and using an Everhart-Thornley SE detector (ETD). The EDS analysis was performed with an energy-dispersive X-ray detector attached to the SEM.

ICP-measurements of pieces of the artifact were carried out at the CCIC Middle East laboratory in Fujairah. For the ICP-OES measurements, an Agilent ICP-OES Model-5110 was used after the digestion of the samples with HNO_3 in a microwave digester.

4.2.1. Soil

Various analytical methods were selected and designed to identify factors influencing soil corrosion. Sarouq Al-Hadid soil samples were collected in plastic bags, dried, and filtered through a 2 mm mesh sieve. The ones retrieved from Al-Qusais were contained in a plastic tube to prevent damaging the graves and were opened and dried in the lab before the experiment. All samples were prepared for analytical studies and other tests at UAEU labs such as measuring soil water and soil organic matter, pH, electrical conductivity test (EC), and characterization of soluble salts. 200 g of each sample of both sites was prepared and sent to Dubai Central Lab (DCL) for analyzing the acid soluble chloride of the soil to understand the soluble ions using the BS 1377-3: 2018+A1 2021 cl. 9.3 method and X-ray fluorescence (XRF).

The water and soil organic matter (SOM) content was measured by weight loss analysis by heating the sample in an oven (Carbolite). 5.0 g of soil was heated at 120°C for 12 h - here the water loss could be calculated. Thereafter, the sample was heated at 600°C for 4 h. At 600°C , organic matter is combusted; however, calcium carbonate does not yet decompose to calcium oxide (calcination) at this temperature. The weight loss of the sample was measured after each step.

For the water-soluble matter, 6.75 g of soil was heated at 120°C for 12h in an oven (Carbolite), again to calculate the water content of the soil. After re-weighing, the cooled soil sample was stirred in 200 mL of deionized water for 30 minutes at room temperature. Then, it was filtered through filter paper (Schleicher and Schuell, 1505). The filtered remaining soil was dried at 37°C , then at 70°C , then at 120°C . The dried soil sample was re-weighed after cooling down.

The pH in the soil was analyzed by a pH meter (Orion model 420A). A conductometer (Orion 50) measured the electrical conductivity (EC) to identify the degree of salinity in the soil-water extract by the 1:2 (v:v) method as follows: mix 20g of soil in 40 ml of de-ionized water, stir it, and keep it for 30 minutes until all the suspended material has equilibrated, measure with the conductometer at 25°C . According to the method, the EC is measured in mmhos cm^{-1} , which divides the degree of salinity into six categories: non-saline, if it is less than 0.40, very slightly saline, if it is between 0.40-0.80, moderately saline, if it is between 0.81-1.20, saline, if it is between 1.21-1.60, strongly saline, if it is between 1.61-3.20 and very strongly saline, if it is larger than 3.20 (Gartley, 2011).

4.2.2. The artifacts

In general, when artifacts are excavated, their surface consists of a massive layer of corrosion product with soil attached. These layers include different components, depending on many factors, such as the composition of the artifact and the surrounding soil. To recognise the massive layer, the corrosion morphology and microstructure of the bronze artifacts are determined. Optical microscopic analysis and X-ray diffraction identify the corrosion products that will help choose the best treatment for the artifact to conserve it adequately, either for a museum exhibition or for a further archaeological study providing information about the historical background of the artifact and the site.

First, optical microscopy is used to visually examine the corrosion morphology and the surface condition. In our case, an AmScope 7x-45x Zoom Trinocular stereomicroscope was used at a 20x magnification level. A digital camera was mounted on the stereomicroscope, and pictures of the artifacts were taken using the AmScope 3.7.1443.20180326 software for all mentioned samples. The optical microscopic pictures show the difference between the surface morphology of objects stemming from the two sites. Second, the same method was used to examine the cross-section of different corrosion layers to identify the corrosion stratigraphy and mechanisms. Third, micro-analytical studies analysed the samples by EDS to determine the surface elemental content of the artifacts. For the analysis, the sample was coated with gold. Fourth, 1g of two samples from each site were sent to the CCIC Middle East laboratory for ICP analysis to identify their bulk elemental content. Fourth, a small amounts powdered corrosion products were collected to determine the corrosion product from objects from each site using an X-ray diffractometer.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The soil samples were analysed to measure the corrosivity factors that influence the buried artefacts degradation rate, helping to understand corrosion types and mechanisms. In general, the results showed that SHS soil is partially corrosive for long-time burial. On the other hand, QUS soil is corrosive for long-time burial. A second major finding relates to the examination of the corrosion morphology and layers to determine optimal ways for corrosion surface removal, whether mechanical or chemical. Based on the data, both sites produce different corrosion morphologies, with SHS creating lower levels of corrosion damage than QUS. However, bronze artifacts from both sites showed the appearance of bronze disease because of the presence of copper chloride (CuCl_2), nantokite (CuCl), and atacamite ($\text{Cu}_2\text{Cl}(\text{OH})_3$).

5.1. Soil Composition and Corrosivity Factors

The chemical composition of the soil samples was analysed by XRD and XRF. Firstly, an XRD spectrum was taken from one sample from each site. In the case of SHS, sample SA.15291 from area F had been collected from deep under the sand dune, and the result is shown in Figure 6. The spectrum indicates the presence of calcite (CaCO_3), quartz (SiO_2), and orthoclase $\text{K}(\text{AlSi}_3\text{O}_8)$. On the other hand, the QUS SQ-12 sample comes from inside grave 309. The corresponding XRD spectrum is shown in Figure 7. The spectrum indicates the presence of calcite (CaCO_3), quartz (SiO_2), orthoclase $\text{K}(\text{AlSi}_3\text{O}_8)$, and the presence of another type of potassium feldspar. An important difference between the two samples is that the QUS sample is especially rich in calcite, while the SHS sample is rich in quartz.

Figure 6. Sampled XRD spectrum of Sarouq Al-Hadid (SA.15291)

Figure 7. Sampled XRD spectrum of Al-Qusais (SQ-12)

The elemental composition of SHS is shown in Table I, where the elements are calculated as oxides. The main components of all samples are SiO_2 (quartz),

CaO , derived from calcite (CaCO_3), Al_2O_3 from aluminosilicates, MgO , partially derived from dolomite (CaMgCO_3), Na_2O , and Fe_2O_3 . Looking at anions,

there is very little sulphate, with SO_3 only at 0.144 ± 0.015 %. Some SO_3 may also derive from sulfidic minerals as some samples give off a smell of H_2S after acidification. This also means that there is very little gypsum in the samples. A 0.01 % chloride content is also quite low; hence the detected sodium is mostly associated with another mineral than with halite (NaCl). A possibility could be sodium aluminosilicates.

Correspondingly, the chemical composition related to QUS is mentioned in Table II, where the elements again are calculated as oxides. The main components of all samples are CaO derived from calcite, SiO_2 (quartz), Al_2O_3 (derived from aluminosilicates),

MgO (derived from dolomite or magnesium aluminosilicates), and Fe_2O_3 , which can derive from hematite or magnetite. Here, it is significant that the CaCO_3 derived Ca content is higher than that in the samples of SHS as could also be seen in the XRD spectra shown above. The chloride, phosphorus, and sulphur contents are higher. This means that some of the sodium will be associated with chloride as halite, and the presence of gypsum in QUS samples is more likely than in the SHS samples. The higher phosphorus content in QUS samples as compared to SHS samples may be due to the fact that the QUS archaeological site is adjacent to a functioning cemetery.

Table I. Chemical composition of Sarouq Al-Hadid samples as analysed by XRF

	Fe_2O_3 (%)	Mn_3O_4 (%)	TiO_2 (%)	CaO (%)	K_2O (%)	SO_3 (%)	SiO_2 (%)	Al_2O_3 (%)	MgO (%)	Na_2O (%)	Cl %	P_2O_5 %
SA.15288	0.958	0.036	0.164	29.716	0.734	0.135	36.308	3.859	1.843	1.077	0.01	0.052
SA.15289	0.958	0.033	0.167	32.454	0.646	0.16	32.081	3.432	1.84	0.936	0.01	0.053
SA.15290	0.998	0.04	0.169	28.638	0.776	0.128	38.666	4.068	1.851	1.126	0.01	0.05
SA.15291	1.127	0.036	0.194	29.817	0.699	0.155	35.353	3.743	2.253	0.995	0.01	0.098
Avg	1.0103	0.0363	0.1735	30.1563	0.7138	0.1445	35.6020	3.7755	1.9468	1.0335	0.0100	0.0633
SD	0.0801	0.0029	0.0138	1.6221	0.0551	0.0154	2.7292	0.2656	0.2042	0.0845	0.0000	0.0232

Table II. Chemical composition of Al-Qusais samples as analysed by XRF

	Fe_2O_3 (%)	Mn_3O_4 (%)	TiO_2 (%)	CaO (%)	K_2O (%)	SO_3 (%)	SiO_2 (%)	Al_2O_3 (%)	MgO (%)	Na_2O (%)	Cl %	P_2O_5 %
SQ-12	1.131	0.04	0.184	32.779	0.678	0.429	30.288	3.52	1.994	0.925	0.13	0.188
SQ-13	1.137	0.039	0.183	34.66	0.61	0.465	26.8	3.284	2.082	0.853	0.12	0.119
SQ-14	1.072	0.036	0.17	33.887	0.635	0.441	28.155	3.282	1.929	0.863	0.12	0.107
SQ-15	0.83	0.029	0.12	38.765	0.498	0.61	21.56	2.485	1.357	0.706	0.19	0.066
SQ-16	1.053	0.035	0.165	33.871	0.64	0.445	28.332	3.257	1.883	0.865	0.13	0.104
SQ-17	1.162	0.045	0.203	33.412	0.637	0.321	28.591	3.42	2.241	0.832	0.03	0.07
SQ-18	1.128	0.04	0.196	34.32	0.615	0.488	27.318	3.258	2.018	1.02	0.19	0.152
SQ-19	1.114	0.039	0.194	34.005	0.623	0.513	27.845	3.288	2.048	1.039	0.21	0.101
SQ-20	1.109	0.041	0.195	34.233	0.613	0.418	27.278	3.245	2.03	0.989	0.23	-
Avg	1.0818	0.0382	0.1789	34.4369	0.6166	0.4589	27.3519	3.2266	1.9536	0.8991	0.1500	0.1134
SD	0.1001	0.0045	0.0254	1.7119	0.0490	0.0781	2.3943	0.2928	0.2452	0.1057	0.0614	0.0405

Practically all samples from the same location present a similar composition. However, the two major components at both sites are CaCO_3 and SiO_2 , the content of which is affected by the distance of the site from the coast, 45 km in the case of SHS and less than 10 km for QUS. This is relevant as the farther the site is from the coast, the higher is the SiO_2 component and the lower the CaCO_3 content. The corrosivity factors in the soil explain the relationship between the

burial artifacts and the surrounding environment. The first factor is the water content of the soil and its water-holding capacity. Soil from the SHS site showed a water content of 0.36% (SA-15288) to 0.89% (SA-15291) and the soil of the QUS site had a slightly higher water content of 0.53% (SQ-17) to 4.71% (SQ-12). The second factor is the organic material loss value (SOM), which in SHS soil with 0.78% (SA-15288) to 2.42% (SA-15291) is smaller than that in QUS

soil with 1.27% (SQ-13) to 6% in (SQ-12), as shown in Figure 8. These values indicate that QUS has a higher water holding capacity than SHS. This can be explained partially by the porosity of the soil particles, in that the soil of SHS has a higher porosity and is less capable of keeping the water inside the soil. However, the texture of the soil also affects the water-holding

capacity factor. The presence of silt in QUS indicates that its water-holding capacity is higher than SHS, and the presence of large amounts of sand in SHS indicates a higher aeration of the soil than at QUS. QUS also possesses a number of hygroscopic materials such as halite.

Figure 8. Water and SOM content diagrams measured for soil samples from SHS and QUS

The third factor to determine the corrosivity of soil is the pH of the soil. The pH of the analysed soil samples is presented in Figure 9. The pH result was taken at 25 °C. The results show that the soil at both sites is slightly alkaline, but it is more alkaline at SHS than at QUS, although QUS has a higher carbonate content.

Furthermore, soil alkalinity is affected by the amount of soil organic matter (SOM) and the presence of nutrients in the soil. When the soil is more alkaline, the SOM content is less as shown in SHS. In QUS the pH is lower, but the SOM is higher.

Figure 9. The pH measurements from Saruq Al-Hadid and Al-Qusais

The fourth factor to determine corrosivity is the chloride (Cl⁻) present in the soil. In SHS the Cl⁻ content is on average 0.01 w% for all samples, which is much lower than that of QUS (0.15 w%). The fifth factor regarding corrosivity is the soil's electrical conductivity (EC), which explains the salinity and is a measure of the presence of soluble salts in the soil. High conductivity indicates the presence of soluble salts, which accelerates the corrosion reaction on the artifact's surface. Figure 10 shows the electrical conductivity results for both sites, showing that EC in QUS is much higher than in SHS. Indeed, the minimum conductivity in QUS is 724 μ S (SQ-17), and the

maximum is 3600 μ S (SQ-16). In general, the soil from this site can be rated as being between saline and very strongly saline. However, samples from inside grave G309 are strongly saline (between 1.8 mS (SQ-13) to 2.1 mS (SQ-12)), but it is very strongly saline (3.6 mS in SQ-16) from the wall of the grave. This indicates that the soil added to the buried bodies is different from the soil from the grave wall, which is the soil of the sabkha environment. The random sample from the yard, SQ-17, is saline (0.7 mS) and but it is of lower salinity than the soil samples stemming from the grave site itself. Finally, two samples from grave G35 are also strongly saline [2.9 mS (SQ-18) and 3.2 mS

(SQ-19)], and one is very strongly saline (3.9 mS in SQ-20). The salinity of grave G309 is lower than grave G35 due to past excavation of grave G35, which could be contaminated with the outer surface soil and not be ancient soil. However, an extra sample was tested from the surface of the site far from the excavation, and the EC was 28.8 mS, which is very high in salinity. This can indicate that opening the grave and retaining the sand without removing the object can increase the corrosivity of the surrounding media. This will affect the artifact negatively. The top surface is not considered archaeological soil, and it is contaminated by the surrounding environment, which can be due to anthropogenic activities, climate change, and other environmental threats. However, the high salinity on this upper surface can affect the salinity of the grave, if it is opened and closed without removing the pre-

sent artifacts as this action will increase the corrosivity of the media inside the grave and affect the artifact negatively. This was observed in Grave 35 (which had been opened previously) which has a higher salinity than Grave 309. As for the conductivity at SHS, the minimum conductivity measured for soil samples from SHS is 66 μS (SA-15291), and the maximum is 81.1 μS (SA-15289). The degree of salinity for all the samples from SHS is hence non-saline. The correlation between soil salinity and soil corrosivity is that the higher the EC, the higher the corrosivity, so the soil environment at QUS is more corrosive than at SHS. The soil corrosivity analysis at both sites showed that each site has a different environment, which affects the burial of archaeological bronze artifacts differently, causing different corrosion mechanisms and morphologies on the objects.

Figure 10. The EC measurements from Saruq Al-Hadid and Al-Qusais

The sixth factor concerning corrosivity is the physical aspect. Soil from the SHS consists of light brown sand with stone and animal bone (it is mentioned that people on the site were using camel bone, but this has not been established by research). The particles appear sandy and moist, with other small black particles that could be part of clay deposits. The deeper under the dune, the moister and darker the soil samples become. The texture of the sand is sandy loam; it is less coherent, and the sand can be felt. On the other hand, at QUS, the soil samples are beige and very thin. There are human bone particles because the soil samples were taken from a tomb, in addition to white particles that could be salt. This is because the site lies in the coastal sabkha. The soil appears sandy but more coherent, smoother, and lighter than at SAH. The seventh and last key factor is porosity and aeration level. As stated above, the porosity level of the SHS surpasses that of the QUS, which may suggest a different water retention capacity for each location. This, in

turn, could impact the corrosion of any bronze artifacts nearby. The sand content in SHS may explain its aeration and drainage capabilities.

5.2. Soil Corrosivity Index (SCI)

Soil corrosivity can be estimated through the Soil Corrosivity Index (SCI) model for archaeological copper, which is established by a combination of seven factors (Oudbashi, 2018): 1- Soil pH (pH), 2- Soil organic matter (SOM), 3- Soil water content (WC), 4- Soil aeration and texture (SA), 5- Electrical conductivity of soil extract (EC), 6- Concentration of soluble chloride anion (Cl^-) (CSC), 7- Total soluble salt (TSS) content measured in the soil. The SCI model equation is the sum of all seven factors which classifies the soil into four groups: non-corrosive, partially corrosive, corrosive, and severely corrosive based on the following equation:

$$\text{SCI} = \text{pH} + \text{SOM} + \text{WC} + \text{SA} + \text{EC} + \text{CSC} + \text{TSS}$$

Figure 11 displays the SCI values of both archaeological sites. First, all values of SHS are 12 which indicates that soil is partially corrosive for long-term burial. On the other hand, most values at QUS are 22 to

23 which indicates that the soil is corrosive for long-term burial, except for QU-17, which is partially corrosive.

Figure 11. Diagram of Soil Corrosivity Index (SCI) in the soil samples from both sites

5.3. Microscopic Observations

Even only from a macroscopic angle, corrosion mechanisms on the artifacts from the two sites are notoriously different, depending on which soil layer the bronze objects were found in. The surfaces of some artifacts from SHS showed a massive corrosion layer with a large accumulation of soil and salt accumulation. Others presented only thin layers of corrosion with loose grains of soil and clear patinas. The massive layers contain various corrosion products, and in some cases, patinas are present and clear. The corrosion products in SHS artifacts vary in colour between green, blue, black, and grey, where their structures vary between waxy and compact structures, crystals, and powders. Identifying the patina in all artifacts is problematic due to several factors, such as the burial environment, composition, manufacture, and finishing procedure (Manti & Watkinson, 2022). Several types of crust (outer surface) formations on the copper alloy artifact surface form during sequential historical periods, such as thin crust, medium crust made of chemical compounds from the surrounding environment, and thick, rough crust with a mineralized compound from its surrounding environment (Sandu et al., 2012).

Systematic examination determined the following morphology for SHS objects: the quartz grain is often large and has different colours, while some of the grains are green due to the powdered corrosion products in between them. In some artifacts, the grains are loose. Salt accumulation is also present and leads to the compacting of the quartz. Furthermore, the corrosion products under the grains are pale green, blue, red, dark green and black. The original surface is clear in some artifacts with a black patina, but some have brown or pitting spots. Long, deep cracks with pale green crystals were found near large quartz grains. A pale brown or yellowish product similar in color to rust [hydrous iron (III) oxide ($\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and iron (III) oxide-hydroxide ($\text{FeO}(\text{OH})$, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$)] was found on some artifacts. It is believed to be tenorite (CuO) in most instances. In general, from QUS, the artifacts' surfaces also showed a massive, thick corrosion layer with small soil grains and compact salt accumulation. The massive layer contains various corrosion products in different green and black colours. The patina was not clear in most cases, but occasionally comes over as red. The major structures of the corrosion products are either compact, crystals, or powders.

Figure 12. OM of SA-3 surface from SHS, showing spots that are likely tenorite (CuO) in the middle of other copper corrosion products.

Figure 13. OM of SA-5(B) surface from SHS, showing a corrosion product (azurite, $\text{Cu}_3(\text{CO}_3)_2(\text{OH})_2$) on top of a stable layer of corrosion or patina.

Figure 14. OM of SA-5(F) surface from SHS, showing a stable patina with circular spots that include corrosion products, likely cuprite, azurite and atacamite.

Figure 15. OM of SA-6 surface from SHS, showing a large crack in the middle of oxidation products that are mixed with sand accumulation. This artifact has a clear patina on another part of its surface.

Figure 16. OM of SA-8 surface from SHS showing the metal structure, the patina, a corrosion product, and the sand accumulation.

Figure 17. OM of another part of the SA-8 surface from SHS.

Figure 18. OM of SA-10 surface from SHS showing different corrosion products of copper alloy in one area with grains of loose sand and a probable tenorite (CuO) area.

Figure 19. OM of SA-11 surface from SHS; another example of salt integration in the surface of the artifact with quartz grain accumulation.

Figure 20. OM of QU-10 from QUS; cracks can be noted on the surface.

Figure 21. OM of QU-2 from QUS. Different corrosion products with sand accumulation can be found. One of the main corrosion products is suggested to be Cassiterite (SnO_2).

Figure 22. OM of QU-3 surface from QUS, illustrating active corrosion.

Figure 23. OM of QU-4 surface from QUS.

Figure 24. OM of QU-5 surface from QUS, showing sand accumulation on top of a corrosion product.

Figure 25. OM of QU-5 surface from QUS. This is another example of patina with active corrosion on top of a flaked area with clear original surface.

Figure 26. OM of QU-7 surface from QUS.

Figure 27. OM of QU-8 surface from QUS.

Microscopic examination showed the following morphologies in QUS samples: some artifacts have different surfaces on opposite sides. Other artifacts have large cracks with pale green crystals. The original surface appears as red to black in the area where the corrosion product is removed, and active corrosion is present as a powder pale green in some artifacts waxy-like product most likely chloride, and a bulk of pale darkish green which is most likely malachite accumulated in a given area (specific details on Figures 12 to 27).

Despite this classification, all bronze artifacts show a complex corrosion profile as a result of external factors such as the chemo-physical properties of the burial environment, and internal factors such as the nature of the metal alloy and the manufacturing techniques (Thunberg et al., 2022). In addition, the corrosion profile could be affected further due to external post-excavation factors such as relative humidity (RH) and air pollutants such as anthropogenic emissions or other gases (Rimmer et al., 2013). Both factors could be lower in SHS than in QUS because of the site's location. Altogether, the morphology of the surfaces shows that QUS artifacts are more affected than their counterparts from SHS. This can be confirmed through the corrosion stratigraphy as well.

The stratigraphy of the corrosion layer is shown in the cross-section of the samples from each site (Fig. 28 and 29), lacking any similarity in their formation. In fact, the layers could be different even in one single artifact, especially visible at the collection from QUS. The metal structure was clear for the majority of the artifacts from SHS, but in QUS artifacts, the metallic structure was transformed completely into corrosion

products in the vast majority cases. The corrosion layers are massive in all artifacts from QUS, while SHS presents some thin ones as well.

Regarding the microscopic studies carried out on the samples, a metal structure in the cross-section of the SHS artifacts was observed in 8 samples, while the others were converted completely to corrosion products. The corrosion layers in the artifacts vary from one artifact to another. However, artifacts with clear patinas and loose sand grains exhibit less corrosion product on their surface than the ones with thick layers of crusts containing different corrosion products varying in colour between black, red, and green. The stratigraphy of the corrosion layers in SHS can be summarized as follows: i) a metallic structure with a thin black patina, ii) a metallic structure covered with massive red, black, and green corrosion layers, and iii) a metallic structure with three layers of black, red, blue, and green colour with active corrosion (AC) under the corrosion layers.

The stratigraphy was recorded as follows: (a) a metal structure in the middle, (b) pale green active corrosion product near the metal structure, (c) black tenorite covers the metal structure and the AC product, (d) the massive corrosion layer which includes (from inside to outside) a black-red layer, red layer, and green layer. A metal structure in the cross-section of the QUS artifacts was observed in 3 samples, but the other seven samples were converted completely to corrosion products, and there were corrosion spots on the remaining metal structures. The cross-sections repeatedly illustrated different corrosion layers in the same artifact.

Figure 28. A cross-section of SA-11 from SHS, showing the stratigraphy of the corrosion layer on top of the metal structure. The stratigraphy is as follows: (a) the metal structure is in the middle surrounded with (b) a thick black-red layer, then (c) a thin layer of the original surface, then (d) a red-blue corrosion crystals, finally (e) the outer green corrosion and quartz grain layer.

Figure 29. A cross-section of QU-3 from QUS with a metal structure in the middle (inner layers) that is converting to a corrosion product. It is covered by a thin layer of green corrosion as a first layer, then follows a black-red corrosion product as a second layer and finally there is the outer layer of sand accumulation and green corrosion products.

The corrosion products are also different from area to area of the sample and vary in their structure (powdery amorphous and crystalline), and in their colour (red, black, pale green, and dark green). The corrosion produces layers of various thickness. The stratigraphy of the corrosion layer on objects from QUS can be summarized as follows: a) remains of a metallic structure with thick black corrosion layers of different thicknesses covering them. The layers can be black, red, and green, b) no metallic structure with an enormous layer of different crystalline black, red, and green corrosion products, with pitting in the inner corrosion layer, c) no metallic structure with a green corrosion product in between a red crust, (d) a thick black corrosion product with massive corrosion layers of red, black and green product and powdered green active corrosion in between them.

The extreme variation in corrosion layers is visible in several of the analysed samples displaying green active corrosion in the middle of a fragment, possibly atacamite between red cuprite and black nantokite.

The formation of the patina and/or corrosion layers on the original surface can be related to two types of corrosion, namely type I and type II. However, the profile of a type I corrosion structure has two layers with no change in the metal and original surface with a clear protective layer, whereas the profile of a type II corrosion structure identifies several layers of metal salt layers, often rich in chloride ions next to the metal structure with no sign of the original surface and unstable layers due to the presence of chloride ions (Thunberg *et al.*, 2022). By comparing the stratigraphy of artifacts from both sites, the conclusion is that most artifacts from SHS suffer from type I corrosion while those from QUS do so from type II.

5.4. Identification of Corrosion Products by XRD

The XRD result of the powdered products extracted from the artifacts showed the following corrosion products, presented in Figures 30 to 35 and also in Table III: cuprite Cu_2O , tenorite CuO , atacamite $\text{Cu}_2\text{Cl}(\text{OH})_3$, azurite $\text{Cu}_3(\text{CO}_3)_2(\text{OH})_2$, nantokite CuCl , malachite $\text{Cu}_2(\text{CO}_3)(\text{OH})_2$, cassiterite SnO_2 , in addition to quartz SiO_2 from the soil.

In SHS the main components are tenorite CuO and cuprite Cu_2O , which were present in all samples. The least abundant corrosion products were cassiterite (SnO_2) and nantokite (CuCl). Other products were the atacamite $\text{Cu}_2\text{Cl}(\text{OH})_3$, azurite $\text{Cu}_3(\text{CO}_3)_2(\text{OH})_2$, and malachite $\text{Cu}_2(\text{CO}_3)(\text{OH})_2$. Quartz SiO_2 and calcite CaCO_3 were detected in some samples.

In QUS, the main corrosion products are tenorite CuO , cuprite Cu_2O , and azurite $\text{Cu}_3(\text{CO}_3)_2(\text{OH})_2$. Nantokite CuCl and cassiterite SnO_2 were not detected in the collected samples.

One can see that the corrosion products are similar in both sites except for the absence of nantokite (CuCl) and cassiterite SnO_2 on the artifact from the Al Qusais site. Malachite can potentially develop after the excavation.

By comparing the results of the XRD spectra regarding the structure of the corrosion products on the artifacts, it is clear that the artifact from SHS included nantokite which is considered part of a stable patina, but the artifact from QUS did not.

Azurite structures can be black or dark blue, but in the crystalline form, which was present on artifacts from both sites, in SHS it was blue and in QUS it was black.

However, it is important to consider that corrosion may have occurred not only during archaeological deposition but also before burial and after excavation (Rimmer *et al.*, 2013). This can explain the presence of several types of corrosion products on one artifact.

Table III. Result of XRD analyses of corrosion products samples from both sites

	Cuprite Cu_2O	Tenorite CuO	Atacamite $\text{Cu}_2\text{Cl}(\text{OH})_3$	Azurite $\text{Cu}_3(\text{CO}_3)_2(\text{OH})_2$	Nantokite CuCl	Malachite $\text{Cu}_2(\text{CO}_3)(\text{OH})_2$	Cassiterite SnO_2	Quartz SiO_2	Calcite $\text{Ca}(\text{CO}_3)$
SH-1	■	■	■	■	-	-	-	-	-
SH-2	■	■	■	■	-	■	■	■	■
SH-3	■	■	■	■	■	■	-	-	-
SH-4	■	■	-	■	■	■	-	■	■
Qu-3	■	■	■	■	-	-	-	-	-
Qu-5	■	■	■	■	-	■	-	■	■

Figure 30. XRD spectrum of SH-1 (GR.23340) from SHS

Figure 31. XRD spectrum of SH-2 (GR.20552) from SHS

Figure 32. XRD spectrum of SH-3 (GR.10911) from SHS

Figure 33. XRD spectrum of SH-4 (GR.20607) from SHS

Figure 34. XRD spectrum of QU-3 from QUS

Figure 35. XRD spectrum of QU-5 from QUS

5.5. SEM-EDS and ICP

To analyse the corrosion products on the immediate surface, an energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopic analysis (EDS) was performed on a newly manufactured bronze sheet serving as a reference for two sam-

ples from QUS (QU-2 and QU-10). As is usual, the detector was attached to a scanning electron microscope. This test was carried out to analyse the elemental composition of the surface to better understand the corrosion products. The samples were gold-coated and the emission band at 2.12 eV in all samples

is associated with the gold coating. The results obtained on a newly manufactured bronze sheet were included as a reference. A peak in the spectrum at 3.44 eV indicates the presence of tin but at a much lower concentration than the expected 8-10%. The results show peaks for Cu, O, Fe, Si, Ca, K, Cl, and Mg. The Si comes from the quartz, which covers the surface of the artifact, and other elements are from the metal structure and the soil component. However, the tin band is not clearly indicated. The analysed area either lacks the tin component or more likely the signal is located within the noise level. This means that the presence of Sn cannot be conclusively shown on the outer layer of the artifact's surface. This result is graphically represented for QU-10, as seen in Figure 36.

From the spectra of this surface area, one may observe the presence of quartz SiO_2 , calcium carbonate CaCO_3 , and corrosion products that include Cl and O, such as cuprite (Cu_2O), tenorite (CuO), and nantokite (CuCl). As the SEM-EDS measurements did not show tin on the surface of the artifacts, small samples of the artifacts were digested and submitted to ICP analysis. This gives an idea of the tin concentration in the bulk of the samples rather than exclusively on the surface. The ICP test results (Table IV) showed that tin is present but in low amounts. The newly manufactured sheet of bronze showed that it contains 93.14% Cu, 2.64% Sn, and 0.65% Zn with Fe (0.01%), Ni (0.01%), and Al (0.002 %) as minor constituents.

Table IV. ICP test results

Test parameter	Copper (Cu) %	Tin (Sn) %	Zinc (Zn) %	Iron (Fe) %	Nickel (Ni) %	Aluminum (Al) %
Sheet of Bronze	93.140	2.640	0.656	0.011	0.011	0.002
SA-5	74.800	2.840	0.451	0.101	0.069	0.042
SA-6	51.320	0.207	0.308	0.331	0.094	0.105
QU-1	57.550	2.740	0.355	0.081	0.042	0.046
QU-2	53.360	3.210	0.331	0.074	0.013	0.019
QU-2 in HCl	54.380	5.930	0.332	0.132	0.133	0.015

In general, the copper content of these bronze artifacts was lower than expected. At QUS, the Cu content is similar between both samples. On the other hand, at SHS, the two samples that were analysed showed different percentages of Cu and Sn; in SA-5, the Cu is 74.8%, and Sn is 2.84%, but in SA-6, Cu is 51.32% (similar to QUS) and Sn content is 0.20%. The low amount of copper in all the artifacts and the variation of the copper concentration is mostly likely due to the varying presence of the corrosion products.

Therefore, Qu-2 was immersed in half conc. HCl for 3 min. at room temperature to remove the outer layer of the corrosion products. ICP of this sample showed a slightly higher concentration of copper than Qu-2 (non-immersed) but importantly showed an appreciably higher tin concentration of 5.93%. Therefore, it can be concluded that the tin leaches out over the time the artifacts are buried, and its concentration near the outer surface layers and in most of the corrosion layers is much diminished.

Figure 36. SEM-EDS of QU-10 from QUS.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The study of corrosion structures on archaeological copper alloy artifacts, distinguishable by their green-grey patina or thick, uneven layer of corrosion, is crucial for their conservation. Especially the understanding of the formation of patina on the different objects of study, whether stable or leading to rapid corrosion, is key to the preservation of the objects and the development of tailored conservation methods.

Several archaeological artifacts were tested from two sites in Dubai, to understand the corrosion mechanisms affecting them as a consequence of their burial environment. The research focused on two distinct archaeological sites: a settlement at Sarouq Al-Hadid (SHS) spanning the time from Prehistory to the Early Islamic period and Al-Qusais (QUS), occupied from the Late Bronze to the Early Iron Age. The results highlight the unique soil corrosivity and patina formation at each site, underscoring the diversity of burial environments.

The first dimension focused on the corrosivity factors of the burial environment affecting archaeological bronzes. Results classified SHS as a partially corrosive environment and QUS as a corrosive environment. Notwithstanding other environmental drivers, the main elements are the presence of organic material content, water-holding capacity, and soluble salt, especially chloride content in the soil.

Secondly, the surface morphologies of the objects differ from site to site in patina and corrosion layer formation, as well as sand accumulation. Black patina development on SHS artifacts is evident on most artifacts with preserved metal structures. In contrast, in QUS, almost all artifacts have several layers of corrosion, with the patina between or under them. Corrosion layers did not appear on all artifacts from SHS, but corrosion products appeared partly as spots and partly in bulk, spread across the surface, while when analysing objects from QUS, it was clear from the cross-section that these corrosion layers are tenden-

tially thick and massive. Finally, the sand accumulation, which forms the outer layer on objects from SHS, is loose, with larger grains that are easy to remove unless they are attached to the corrosion bulk. On objects from QUS, the sand accumulation on the surface is more compact, and the grains are small and combined with the outer corrosion layer. By comparing the patina formation and the burial environment, the conclusion is that separate burial environments affect buried archaeological copper alloy objects differently during

long-term burial, leading to particular corrosion mechanisms and morphologies.

In addition, results showed that the corrosion products are mostly the same at both sites: cuprite Cu_2O , tenorite CuO , and azurite $\text{Cu}_3(\text{CO}_3)_2(\text{OH})_2$. However, nantokite CuCl and cassiterite SnO_2 were only found on objects from SHS. Moreover, the tin concentration was found to be lower on the corrosion layer than the bulk, which indicates that it is concentrated on the metal structure and isolated from the corrosion layer.

LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The artifacts used in this paper were retrieved during fieldwork at SHS between 2017 and 2019 and at QUS in 2020. Taking this into account, the results of this study could be affected by some post-excavation corrosion. As mentioned, artifacts may undergo corrosion before burial, and after excavation. The rate of such a process will depend on many factors, such as the relative humidity and air pollutants post-excavation that accelerate corrosion. Ideally, the artefact should be examined immediately after excavation to study the corrosion behaviour under burial conditions.

A recommendation for further study is trying to determine the metal concentration during the manufacturing stages of bronze objects and to establish compositional differences in samples from other archaeological sites in the region. This can improve the understanding of the corrosion behaviour of such objects in the specific environment of Dubai for better conservation and restoration efforts. In addition, it would be beneficial to develop a new, non-toxic corrosion inhibitor (CI) that can effectively combat corrosion products found on Dubai's archaeological bronzes. This development would be of great interest to the field of archaeological preservation, offering safer and more sustainable solutions to heritage management.

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